

Gaps in Compliance with Maternal and Child Health Interventions in Anambra State, Southeast Nigeria: A Qualitative Study

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Abstract

Introduction: *Despite the available interventions to curb child mortality, African countries south of the Sahara still account for half of the estimated 5.2 million deaths of under-5 children globally, with Nigeria ranking as the highest global contributor. Among interventions targeted at improving child health in Nigeria are childhood immunization, maternal antenatal care, and provision of insecticide treated bed-nets (ITN). However, compliance-related issues with these interventions abound. This study aimed at understanding the socio-cultural and contextual factors influencing compliance with these interventions in Anambra State, Nigeria, and deduces which of them has the best compliance.*

Methods: *A qualitative approach using in-depth interview (IDI) of senior health workers and focus group discussion (FGD) with purposively selected participants was employed. The FGD sessions were conducted separately for women and men.*

Results: *There were 103 participants aged between 22 - 55 years, comprising 97 (women = 50; men = 47) for FGD, and 6 (all women) for IDI sessions. Our findings suggest adequacy of immunization service, adequate compliance with antenatal services, and good awareness about, and ownership of, ITNs. However, there are gaps in compliance with these interventions due to factors like religious beliefs, adverse events following immunization, and inadequate knowledge and equipment for setting up the ITNs.*

Conclusions: *Our findings show both availability and adequacy of the studied interventions in the area, but with gaps in the compliance level of the people. Failure to close the identified gaps therefore may impede the ability of the state to meet up with the SDG goals for health.*

Keywords: Antenatal care, child health, Anambra state, maternal health, under-5-mortality.

Introduction

High death rates among children under-5 years remains a pressing global health concern. According to the United Nations Children's Fund [UNICEF][1] an estimated 5.2 million children aged < 5 years died in 2019. However, there is wide disparity in child mortality rates between the developed and the developing countries, with a concomitant imbalance in child survival between children born in developing, compared to those born in developed countries[2]. The situation is particularly worrisome in African countries south of the Sahara, where infant and child mortality rates are 10 times higher than those in developed countries[3], with over 50% of under-5 deaths globally occurring within the region in 2019[1]. In the latest report on global child mortality, UNICEF estimated that approximately 857,900 under-5 children died in Nigeria in 2019, placing the country as the highest contributor to under-5 mortality globally[4]. Currently, the under-5 mortality rate in the country is 120 per 1000 live births[5]. This level is more than quadruple the target set for the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) of 25 deaths per 1000 live births that countries are expected to attain by 2030[6]. Moreover, there are wide geographical disparities in the distribution of under-5 mortality in the country, with some states recording rates as high as 210 per 1000, whereas the state with the lowest under-5 mortality rate was 45 per 1000[5]. This reality calls for efforts to understand the drivers of under-5 mortality in Nigeria, which will help inform tailored approaches for trend reversal.

Generally, several factors are implicated in the high rate of under-5 mortalities within Nigeria. These include infectious diseases such as malaria, diarrhea; pre-term births; and complications associated with pregnancy and delivery, as well as childhood malnutrition[4,7,8]. Therefore, life-saving interventions such as maternal antenatal care (ANC), childhood immunization, and other curative and preventive strategies are imperative to the reversal of child mortality. However, despite the availability of these interventions, Nigeria has not fared well in its utilization for tackling child morbidity and mortality. In addition to issues related to access and poor coverage for some interventions[9], in several cases, poor compliance with delivery and application of these interventions is at the root of their ineffectiveness[10,11]. Factors that have been reported to influence compliance with child health interventions include education and age of the mother, social support and perception about treatment, distance to health centers, cost of health services, cultural beliefs and attitude of health workers[12–14].

In Anambra State, southeast Nigeria, the lack of compliance with child health interventions has continued to affect the health of children in different ways. A report from the 2013 Nigerian Demographic and Health Survey showed that only 51.6% of the children received all basic vaccines. Insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) did not show better compliance than vaccine coverage because fewer children (14.1%) and pregnant women (13.8%) used ITNs. ANC attendance showed that more than 16% of pregnant women did not use ANC services, with 11.3% delivering at home. Overall, almost half (48.5%) of the mothers had at least one problem with

Received: 03 February 2025

Revised: 12 February 2025

Accepted: 24 February 2025

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14916558>

the implementation of health interventions in the state[15]. Thus, while infectious diseases clearly play an important role in childhood morbidity and mortality, high rates of major childhood diseases in the state have been attributed to non-compliance with available child health interventions[16].

Thus, it became imperative for a critical study to elucidate the drivers and factors contributing to noncompliance with child health interventions in the state. The need for such a study is even more imperative, given that while the issue bordering on compliance may be virtually the same in most Nigerian states, the actual manifestation and explanatory factors may differ from one locality to another, and even among social groups within the same society. Therefore, this study was conducted to identify the sociocultural factors affecting compliance with attendance at ANC, ITN usage, and immunization services (IS) utilization, and deduce which of them are complied with most by mothers, using data from Anambra State, Nigeria.

Methods

Design of the study

A qualitative approach was adopted to elicit information on the behaviors and sociocultural characteristics of the people that could influence their compliance with child health interventions. The study was limited to investigating compliance with the three key child health interventions, including immunization services, ITN usage, and utilization of antenatal care services. This was accomplished using both in-depth interviews (IDI) and focus group discussions (FGD) conducted among purposively selected participants.

Study setting

This study was conducted in Anambra State, southeastern Nigeria. The state lies on rolling flat land in the eastern plains of the River Niger and covers an area of 4,416Km². The population is currently estimated at 10.8 million[17]. Anambra State shares common borders with Enugu, Delta, Imo, and Kogi States to the east, west, south, and north, respectively. There are 21 Local Government Areas and approximately 1394 communities[17]. The dominant language in the state is Igbo, and Christianity is the predominant religion. Three local governments were selected for the study and are: Onitsha South, Nnewi North, and Orumba North local government areas (LGA) representing urban, semi-urban, and rural settlements respectively. Communities and participants for the FGD and IDI were purposively sampled and administered the research instrument.

Type of participants/materials involved

In each community, FGD participants were identified and invited to participate in the sessions by key informants (KI) who were members of the community. A total of 12 (twelve) FGD sessions

were conducted, two per community, with separate sessions for women and men. Each FGD session was comprised of eight participants of the same sex. The homogeneity of the sex of participants allows for ease of discussion of issues that may be particular to each sex, which they may not be comfortable discussing in mixed sex groupings[18]. However, in one of the FGD sessions for women in the Awgbu community in Orumba North LGA, there were 10 participants, and only seven participants in an FGD session for men in Nnewi North LGA. The IDI was conducted by the first author with the six most senior health workers drawn purposively from primary healthcare centers (PHCs) in the six communities under study. Most senior health workers were selected because of their experience in working with women of child-bearing age.

The FGD sessions were moderated by the first author, who relied on the FGD guide to elicit participants' views. Responses were recorded by a research assistant who also took notes during sessions. IDI was also conducted with selected health workers using the IDI guide. Responses were recorded and transcribed verbatim after each session. To mitigate attrition, FGD sessions were scheduled during periods suitable for the participants. This was done to ensure convenience and data quality.

Patients and public involvement

This research is co-produced with the study participants who voluntarily participated in the study including co-recruitment of focus groups. However, the authors retained discretionary rights about what information to include in quoted excerpts from study respondents. Participants in the study did not have prior disclosure of the study findings—and waived this right accordingly in the consent forms they signed.

Data analysis

The analysis of the qualitative data was descriptive. This was performed using a manual analysis relying on Microsoft Word. Emphasis was placed on the interpretation, description, triangulation, and recording/writing of responses from the FGDs and IDIs. The information gathered was transcribed and phrases with contextual or special connotations were noted and pulled out as illustrative quotes to support the research themes.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical clearance for this study was obtained from the National Health Research Ethics Committee of the University of Nigeria Teaching Hospital, Enugu (NHREC/05/01/2008B-FWA00002458-IRB00002323). Before each interview and FGD session, verbal and written informed consent was obtained from all the participants. They were informed that the responses were voluntary, could be stopped at any time, and assured of confidentiality and anonymity. Names and biomarkers (sex or age) of respondents were not included in the transcribed texts.

Results

The analysis of participants' responses yielded insights into the pivotal themes of this research study. These themes surround immunization service (IS), ANC services, and ITN utilization.

Immunization service delivery

The theme of immunization service delivery focused on the availability, assessment of, and barriers to the uptake of childhood immunization. Responses from the research participants are further granulated into the following subthemes:

Multi-prong approaches to immunization service delivery

Our results show the availability of immunization services for childhood immunization in all the studied locations. Participants noted the multi-prong approaches deployed in the delivery of the service, including women taking their children to health centers and community outreaches by health workers from the health centers.

“Even that immunization the people of Nnewi south go for it very well. If you go to a general or private hospital and do not perform the immunization, they will announce in the church that they will do the immunization here or there. If you do not turn up, they will carry their immunization materials and equipment and go house to house to carry out the immunization exercise.” (Participant 3, FGD for women, semi-urban area)

Another respondent noted something similar:

“Even on Sundays, the immunization health workers go to churches to carry out the immunization exercise...The workers go to school as well for the exercise. The mothers and fathers here in this community know that immunizing the child is important, so they comply.” (Participant 2, FGD for women, urban area).

Barriers to immunization uptake

Some of the most common reasons for non-compliance with routine childhood immunization include religious beliefs, children becoming ill on scheduled immunization days, and some adverse events following immunization (AEFI).

“The reason why some people do not take their children for immunization is that for some, when they administer the child immunization drugs, it causes the child to start running body temperature. Some people do not like to take the immunization drugs. For me it gave my child fever.” (Participant, FGD for women, rural area)

Relatedly, another participant noted:

“Some people say it is because of the church they attend; that they believe it is the duty of their church to cure them and the child if they fall ill.” (Participant 1, FGD for women, urban area).

One element of compliance that was further explored relates to the parents’ compliance with the immunization day scheduled by the health center. Lack of compliance in this area is mainly due to parents’, especially mothers’ occupation.

“Some people shift the date for immunization because of the type of business the mother does. The type of business the mother does may make her miss the exact date for immunization.” (Participant 5, FGD for women, urban area).

It is, however, important to note that people who do not comply are in the minority.

Antenatal Care (ANC) Services

In exploring the theme of ANC service utilization, the researchers sought to determine if the women complied with attendance at antenatal clinics, at what stage of pregnancy they begin ANC, possible reasons people may not utilize ANC services, and alternative places people seek ANC services apart from health centers/clinics. Our results suggest a high level of compliance with ANC services.

“Yes, pregnant women comply very much.” (Participant 1, FGD for women, semi-urban area)

Another participant remarked:

“They are trying. When we came newly, the turn up was not encouraging until a vehicle with speakers was used to sensitize the people on the importance of ANC then pregnant women began to really turn up for the ANC.” (IDI participant, urban area).

In some areas with lower compliance, the introduction of incentives such as the distribution of insecticide-treated nets increased compliance.

“They do not really come out for ANC. But since they started issuing ITNs they started coming because of the incentive. Before, you will see only 3 or 4 in the whole month that will come for ANC but like this month, we have had up to 10 women.” (IDI participant, urban area).

There is no specific gestational age at which the women seek ANC service. Commencement of ANC service depends on several factors, including parity, pregnancy-associated morbidities, and biological differences between women.

“There are some that, if they are one month pregnant their pregnancy starts to give them problems and so they go for antenatal. There are some that don’t have early disturbances and they spend three to four months at home before going for antenatal. So, it all depends on the biology of the person. For example, some women spend seven months at home before they go for antenatal. Those that spend seven months at home are mostly those that have had a child or children before; but those that are in their first pregnancy are new to the experience, so they take no chances by registering for antenatal as early as one or three months.”
(Participant 2, FGD for women, urban area).

Also, there are various reasons people may not subscribe to ANC services. These range from irrational fears like pharmacophobia, to socio-economic factors such as poverty.

“The first one is the fear of drugs. Pregnant women are usually scared to take drugs. Some of them say that the drugs affect their stomachs and when they see the drugs they start to cry. While others when you give them the drugs, they will take it and hide it under their bed. Another one that prevents some women from going for ANC care is the issue of money. Because of this they might not go early for the ANC. The woman might because of lack of money carry the pregnancy up to 9 months before she goes for ANC.” **(Participant 1, FGD for women, semi-urban area).**

One of the salient issues that emerged from interrogating the theme of ANC services utilization borders on the alternative source of ANC services outside the confines of organized modern healthcare practices. Our results show some women would rather patronize traditional and private birth attendants.

“They go to the traditional birth attendant” **(Participant 1, FGD for women, semi-urban area).**

Another participant observed that:

“They go to private birth attendants (PBA). At least I know two women in this community that make delivery but are not health workers. It is true that some people (PBAs) combine western medicine and herbal

medicine, I have heard but I have not gone there” (IDI Participant, rural area).

Insecticide Treated Nets (ITNs) usage

Insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) are among the lifesaving technology-driven solutions for child health. The study further inquired on participants’ knowledge of malaria prevention approaches in children with emphasis on ITNs, ITNs ownership, and sleeping under ITNs. The findings of the study showed that most people know about ITN and have ITN.

“[...] The use of ITNs prevents mosquito attacks and as a result, prevent malaria. So, it is important for the child and mother to make use of ITNs so that they will be okay. [...]” (IDI participant, urban area)

Another reacts:

“Yes, they use the ITNs here. They mostly use it when the mosquitoes are much. And the immunization health workers also help tell the government to issue more ITNs to help combat malaria.” (IDI participant, urban area)

However, it appears the ITNs are not equitably distributed between urban and rural settings, and there is a further inequity in its distribution in the rural location.

“I want the government to make sure the ITNs are evenly distributed among the community members. Sometimes when they issue these nets, they say we should go to the local government to get the nets where they give preferential treatments; sometimes, that makes people tired and discouraged” (Participant 1, FGD for men, rural area).

Also, there is a palpably low level of compliance with ITN use. The reasons given for this include warm ambient temperature, inadequate knowledge, and equipment for setting up the ITN, and individual disposition to the device, including uncomfortable feeling while sleeping under the net.

“People do not use the ITNs because it causes heat. People also do not use the net because of the stress encountered during the preparation or setting of the net. The makers of the nets did not make it to be convenient for people to use. That is why some people do not use it” (Participant, FGD for women, urban area).

The low level of compliance with ITN use might not be unconnected with the inadequate knowledge on the etiology of malaria among the people. While many of the participants erroneously believe that malaria is caused by mosquitoes only, others mention some environmental factors that promote breeding of mosquitoes as a risk factor for malaria. However,

certain things like food and drinks came up from the respondents as the causes of malaria.

“Mosquitoes and too much oil consumption” (Participant 1, FGD for men, urban area).

Another male interviewee says that:

“There was a certain day I went to the market, and I was talking to someone when I overheard one telling someone else that ‘the palm oil you are taking will give you malaria.’ So as the health worker, I turned and told them that palm oil does not cause malaria.” (Emphasis added. IDI participant, urban area).

Discussions

This study has explored the level of compliance with child health intervention in Anambra State, south-east Nigeria through a qualitative approach. Findings showed that there are variations in compliance with the studied health interventions for children. With respect to immunization services, it could be inferred that there is adequate provision of services with multiple strategies deployed to ensure proper coverage. Also, the level of compliance with service uptake by the people is moderately high as responses from research participants suggest. However, some barriers to service uptake identified include religious beliefs, children becoming sick on scheduled immunization days, and some adverse events following immunization (AEFI). Also, there is often non-compliance on the part of the parents with the scheduled date for the child’s immunization. The critical reason this usually occurs is due to the parents’, especially, mother’s occupation with some mothers working as commercial traders, artisans (bakery), and schoolteachers. The findings on immunization services agree with the outcome of the 2016/17 Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey (MICS) that showed 55.2% coverage for full vaccination for children aged 12 to 23 months in Anambra State[5]. Also, our findings are in line with another study that showed high percentage of utilization of routine immunization services by communities in Anambra State[19]. However, our inference could be less empirical as it is based on subjective assessment of qualitative response compared to objective assessment of a quantitative study.

Also, previous studies have identified socio-cultural and economic factors as barriers to healthcare uptake and utilization in Nigeria. For example, Adedini *et al* reported on the role of cultural factors such as ethnicity, and resource-related factors like inadequate financial access as barriers to healthcare utilization in Nigeria[9,20]. In line with our findings that AEFI could be a reason for non-compliance with immunization programme, Oli *et al* reported that 30.7% of research participants are non-compliant with immunization due to “perceived fear of adverse reaction.”[21] The role of parents’, especially mother’s occupation as a determinant of immunization compliance has also been recognized by other researchers. In a systematic review

by Bangura *et al*, housewives were reported to have higher compliance than those engaged in other occupations like trading or being employed in public or private institution.[22]

More so, like immunization services, our findings suggest the availability and relatively high level of compliance with ANC services in the study area. In some areas where there are seemingly low levels of compliance (such as the rural areas), introduction of incentives such as distribution of insecticide-treated nets to the women led to improved compliance. Also, commencement of ANC services is not directly linked to a precise factor. Influencing factors include previous pregnancy, patients' parity, and presence or absence of pregnancy-associated morbidities. Nevertheless, there is evidence that not all the people in the study area subscribe to ANC services. Some of the reasons for non-compliance include pharmacophobia[23], and socio-economic factors like poverty. Apart from persons who do not use ANC services, there are also those who obtain their ANC services from alternative sources such as traditional birth attendants (TBAs). Poverty, as well as living in rural communities, appears to be the key driver for this behavior.

Relatedly, access to ANC services and its associated variables, including skilled birth attendance, and detection and treatment of pregnancy-associated morbidities are the main risk factors for maternal and child health outcome in the period before, during, and after pregnancy[24]. Low access to ANC was found to be associated with increased stillbirths according to the 2016 Global Burden of Disease Study[24]. The observation that there is high level of compliance with ANC attendance in this study is in line with the result of the 2016/17 MICS that showed 98.3% ANC services in Anambra State were rendered by skilled providers, and 90% of the women having 4 or more ANC visits before child birth[5]. In spite of this, there is need for increased access to ANC services in the rural areas in order to ensure statewide attainment of the SDG 3 goal of ending "preventable deaths of newborns and children under 5 years of age" by 2030[25]. This is because evidence shows that maternal and child health indices in Nigeria are extremely low among the rural and poor population[26,27]. One of the ways to achieve this is by incentivizing women to attend ANC services in government-owned health facilities as our study finds that compliance increases during distribution of ITNs. Also, maternity centers can be used for distribution of cash-transfer since economic empowerment of women has been recommended as a means to addressing inequitable access to healthcare[27].

Economic empowerment of women will also help in addressing the barriers to uptake of ANC services identified in this study and promote attendance of ANC in government-owned facilities compared to TBAs. Previous studies in Indonesia identified physical distance and financial barriers as major factors why community members could not utilize services from modern healthcare facilities and prefer TBAs[28]. Also, excessive cost has been found as a major reason women deliver at home or elsewhere[29]. Despite that, users in our study express satisfaction

with services rendered by TBAs, this may not agree with available evidence. Studies show that pregnancy outcome has been found to be associated with the ownership status of the ANC facilities, with patrons of government-owned facilities experiencing reduced child mortality and receiving better quality of service[30,31]. Nevertheless, TBAs are important human resources in settings with inadequate trained health workers, and training them within the framework of task-shift model[32] will bring about improved service and better maternal and child health outcome[28].

As we have discussed, malaria remains one of the leading infectious risks to maternal and child health as the greatest burden of malaria is borne by pregnant women and under-5 children[7,33]. Vector control for malaria prevention leverages on the use of ITNs to reduce human contact with mosquitoes at their peak feeding hours[33]. The findings of this study show that there is a high level of awareness about ITN with a corresponding high level of ITN ownership in the study area. However, there appears to be inequity in the distribution of the ITNs in the rural areas, resulting from perceived preferential treatment in allotment by the health workers. The ITN usage however does not appear to align with its ownership as most of the respondents admitted to not using the bed-nets. The observation from this study explains the low level of percentage (24.1%) of household members in Anambra State who slept under ITN during the previous night as recorded in the 2016/17 MICS[5]. This, even though 37.7% of households in the state had access to ITNs, according to the survey. Also, apart from reasons such as feeling uncomfortable under the net, adduced for non-usage, our findings also suggest that inadequate knowledge of malaria etiology among the people might have contributed to non-compliance. Some of the respondents mentioned consumption of oily and fried food as the cause of malaria. Beyond efforts to distribute ITN therefore, there is need to further educate the people on the etiology of malaria and positive effect of compliance with ITN usage.

Relationship of findings to theoretical framework

The integrated behavioral model (IBM) construct of health behavior posits that an individual's intention is often "the determinants of the likelihood of performing a specific behavior"[34]. Using this model, we attempted contextual underpinnings of the factors influencing compliance with the health interventions, especially ITN usage.

IBM recognizes five factors that determine the likelihood that an individual will perform certain behaviors. These are: motivation to perform the behavior, the knowledge and skill to carry out the behavior, environmental impediments to performance of said behavior, saliency of the behavior to the individual, and the individual's experience in performing the behavior. When applied to ITN usage in our study for example, low level of compliance can be said to be due to lack of a strong intent to use ITN and inadequate skill and knowledge for setting them up. Secondly, certain environmental impediments such as hot ambient temperature prevented the

people from using the ITN. Thirdly, many people do not see ITN use as very important; and finally, although the people have experience with using ITN, the experience was de-motivating rather than encouraging consistent usage. These observations should therefore be integrated into designing health policy for ITN usage, and communication for health promotion of ITN usage. Similar theoretical understanding was adduced for immunization and ANC services (not elaborated here) and led to our position that experienced mothers can be engaged as mentors to aspiring mothers to inspire them to maintain compliance with these interventions. Doing this will go a long way in driving down maternal and child mortality, and help the state in attaining the SDG goals for health[25].

Limitations of the study

While this study has helped to elucidate the contextual and social-cultural factors that could influence the compliance of the people of Anambra state with some maternal and child health interventions, there are however certain limitations that should be considered while interpreting the findings of this study. Firstly, the results are based on the view of respondents which are often subjective due to certain preconceived biases that influenced some of the responses. More so, the perspectives unraveled in this study may not represent generalist views on issues raised across the entire country of Nigeria. It may be convenient to say, however, that this is a limited view of Anambra people and can be representative of the prevailing disposition across the state, and probably south-east Nigeria.

Conclusion

This study has established the social and contextual determinants of compliance with maternal and child health interventions in Anambra State, south-east Nigeria. Our results show both availability and adequacy of interventions of interest. However, there are differing levels of gaps in the compliance of the people with these interventions, with low non-compliance with immunization services and antenatal care, and pronounced non-compliance with ITN usage. Some of the barriers to compliance include personal idiosyncrasies, pharmacophobia and fear of AEFI, inadequate knowledge and skills for personal implementation of interventions, and lack of financial resources for logistics associated with obtaining some of the interventions. While the state may appear to fare better than some other states of the country with regards to compliance with these interventions, failure to close the identified gaps, however, may impede the ability of the state to meet up with the sustainable development goals for health. To close the identified gaps therefore, the government of Nigeria (GoN) could work with development and donor partners at the forefront of ITN interventions to implement a national qualitative study that will help to understand the socio-cultural and structural barriers that hinder effective utilization of ITNs. Findings from such research will assist in policy and program modifications that will help in reducing the malaria burden in the country.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interest.

Funding

The authors have not declared a specific grant for this research from any funding agency in the public, commercial or not-for-profit sectors.

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Received: 03 February 2025

Revised: 12 February 2025

Accepted: 24 February 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.14916558](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14916558)

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